

Electrosynthesis and characterisation of CdSeHgTl thin films

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Abstract : Thallium containing CdSeHg films have been electrosynthesised at -0.600 V vs SCE on titanium substrate from the aqueous solution. Electrochemical properties of the films were investigated in I_2/I^- -redox solution. Films were found to be *p*-type conductor with charge carrier level 10^{25} . The carrier concentration, flat band potential of the film were determined from capacitance measurements. The films were characterized with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) combined with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX) system. The corrosion characteristics of the films have been studied by polarization technique. The inhibitor, inhibits corrosion effectively even in trace amount. This is the study to investigate the effect of thallium concentration on the composition, capacitance, photoactivity, morphology and corrosion parameters of the CdSeHgTl films electrosynthesised by electro deposition.

Keywords : Semiconductors, thin film, electrosynthesis.

Semiconductors belonging to group II to group VI metal compounds are used in a wide range of electrochemical applications including solar energy conversion and photovoltaic devices¹. CdSe is one of the most promising material for solar energy conversion because it has low energy gap and direct optical transition takes place². Several methods have been used to prepare the thin films. Electrochemical method is useful for preparing polycrystalline materials³. In this paper, we have reported the electrosynthesis of Tl containing CdSeHg films and their characterization on the basis of electrochemical, corrosion, compositional and morphological analysis.

Experimental

CdSe films were electrodeposited potentiostatically from aqueous solution on the titanium sheet (1×1 cm). Electrosynthesis was carried out from the solution containing 0.1 M CdSO₄ and 0.01 M SeO₂. The deposition potential was maintained at -0.600 V vs saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Various concentration of Hg and thallium were added to the solution of CdSe during deposition. The chemicals CdSO₄ (C.D.H.), SeO₂ (C.D.H.) < TlNO₃ (A.R.) and HgNO₃ (A.R.) were used without pretreatment. A three electrode cell was used for electrodeposition. A clean titanium plate and SCE were used as counter electrode and reference electrode respectively. The back side of substrate is connected with a copper wire with the help of silver paste and dried. The power supply

(Systronics) was used for application of the potential for deposition. Digital multimeters were used for current and potential measurements. Electrochemical deposition was carried out at room temperature and the electrodes were kept in electroplating solution for about one hour for equilibration. The morphology and composition of the films were investigated with using SEM (JOEL) equipped with EDAX (JOEL). The CdSe, Hg and Tl containing CdSe films are used for measurement of electrical properties. The photoelectroactivity studies were carried out in the redox system containing 1 M (CH₃COO)₂Cd, KI and I₂. The capacitance measurements was done with the help of a digital LCR meter (Systronics). For corrosion behaviour, the electrodeposits were used as working, titanium as counter and SCE as a reference electrode.

Results and discussion

Concentration of Tl in the electrolytic solution containing CdSeHg is an important variable governing the composition of the electrodeposited films. The ratio of the ions in the electrolyte can be varied by either changing the relative concentration of the ions while keeping the total content the same or by varying the concentration of one of the ion while keeping the other constant. In the present study we have followed the latter technique and change the composition by varying the Tl concentration in the electrolyte. Electrochemical deposition of CdSeHg thin films and CdSeHg containing different concentration

Table 1. Electrochemical and corrosion characteristics of CdSeHgTl thin films

Composition of electroplating solution				Deposition current (mA cm ⁻²)		Film thickness (10 ⁻⁵ cm)	Photo-potential	Charge carrier	Corrosion (MPY)
Cd	Se	Hg	Tl	Initial	Final				
0.1	0.01	0.0005	0.0000	1.50	0.12	2.50	150	0.95	2.85
0.1	0.01	0.0005	0.0002	1.75	0.24	5.62	170	1.23	1.24
0.1	0.01	0.0005	0.0004	1.95	0.26	6.91	230	6015	1.10
0.1	0.01	0.0005	0.0006	2.16	0.32	9.50	325	9.33	0.85
0.1	0.01	0.0005	0.0008	2.85	0.38	12.35	215	7.31	1.35
0.1	0.01	0.0005	0.0010	3.40	0.62	15.55	205	4.58	2.12

of Tl was carried out at deposition potential -0.600 V vs SCE. The experimental conditions under which electrosynthesis of CdSeHg and Tl containing CdSeHg films of variable composition were carried out are summarized in Table 1. Fig. 1 shows the concentration of Tl inclusion in the films as a function of initial and steady

Fig. 1. Variation of deposition current : (◆) initial and (●) steady state.

state current density. The Tl content in the electroplating solution increases from 2 to 10 ml with an increase in current density from -1.700 to -3.400 mA. During deposition, current decreases very fast initially to a plateau. The relative speed with which the current decreases during deposition is expected to depend on quality of the deposits in terms of effective coverage of the substrate. The thickness values (Table 1) of the films are estimated from the quantity of charge passed through the electrolyte. Variation of current with time during deposition is shown in Fig. 2. Diffusion coefficient is 15.

The films obtained using various concentration of Tl in CdSeHg were studied for their photo activity using I₂/I-redox solution. The results are given in Table 1. The electrodeposits containing Tl shows improved photo activity up to 0.0006 M concentration. The slopes from

Fig. 2. Variation of current with time during deposition of CdSeHg thin film.

linear portion of Mott-Schottky plot⁴, dc_2/dE decreases as the concentration of Tl was increased. The slopes are used to evaluate charge carrier density. Flat band potential are also comes from the intersection of curve at potential axis.

Fig. 3 shows that the composition relation of Tl between electroplating solution and deposited films. The

Fig. 3. Composition relation on Tl between (■) electroplating solution and (●) deposited films.

ratio of the metals in the film is usually different from that in the electrolyte. It may be noted that Tl concentration in the films is always less than that in the electroplating solution for all concentration of Tl employed in the study. This indicates that the more noble metal is preferentially depositing in the film. When the Tl in the electrolyte is increased from 2 ml to 10 ml, the Tl in the films increase from 1 to 8 atomic percentage, implying that, at higher concentration of Tl in the electroplating solution more of its deposited than at its lower concentration in the solution. The broken line in the Fig. 3 is a reference line along which Tl concentration is plotted to be same in the film and in the electroplating solution as well.

The surface morphology of the electrodeposited films were studied by scanning electron micrograph images. Fig. 4 shows the SEM of electrodeposit (a) CdSeHg and (b) 0.0002 M Tl containing CdSeHg films. From these micrographs we can draw some conclusion i.e.

- (i) The films are continuous and homogenous.
- (ii) The films appear to be polycrystalline in nature and densely packed.
- (iii) The morphology of these films is affected by Tl incorporation.
- (iv) The grains of the deposits at increased Tl content

Fig. 4(a). SEM of CdSeHg.

Fig. 4(b). SEM of Tl containing CdSeHg.

appeared clearer and larger than that of CdSeHg.

The comparison of SEM reveals a increase in the grain size with the increase in Hg and Tl content. Shape of grains also changes. The typical particle size varies from 50 μm to 5 μm . A larger particles of about 10 μm of CdSe is also obvious in the case of 0.0010 M Tl containing CdSe. Fig. 5 shows the energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX) of the deposited films from the same solution and under the same condition as in Fig. 4. The EDAX analysis indicates that the inclusion of Tl in the deposits are as like as in electroplating solution i.e. the inclusion of on increasing the concentration of Tl in the electroplating solution, increased the Tl content in deposited films also.

Fig. 5(a). EDAX of CdSe.

Fig. 5(b). EDAX of CdSeHg.

Fig. 5(c). EDAX of 0.006 M Tl containing CdSeHg.

Fig. 6. A typical Tafel plot (■) in presence and (●) in absence of inhibitor.

The Tafel plots carried at room temperature in I_2/I^- redox solution with and without inhibitor. Both anodic and cathodic Tafel plots in each case shifted towards higher polarization level in presence of inhibitor. From the polarization curve, the corrosion current densities were estimated using the relationship

$$I_{\text{corr}} = \frac{ba \cdot bc}{2.303 (ba + bc)} \cdot Rp$$

where Rp is the polarization resistance, ba and bc are the anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes respectively. The corrosion rates of the electrosynthesised films were calculated with the help of the equation

$$CR = 0.13 I_{\text{corr}} (EW)/d$$

where EW is the equivalent weight and d is the density of deposited materials. The corrosion current decreases with the addition of TI and the inhibitor i.e. glycine and benzotriazole also.

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